

The Image Of Women In The Holy Quran

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Abstract

The research attempted to demonstrate the image of woman in the Holy Quran and eliminate the erroneous ideas that were wrongly viewed by people about the great position that women gained in the Holy Quran, where it illustrated real images and models for women within two routes; one of them is for making good examples and the other for avoidance. The view in these two routes was similar to that of men, in that it was fair in discourse and treatment based on equal opportunities and human dignity regardless gender, in which the wise miraculous context was displayed in a realistic way. The offered models demonstrated the position of woman as a mother, wife and a leader. The study focused on demonstrating the origin to which humanity belongs; the same entity from which Adam and Eve were created, in that there is no preference for one over the other.

Introduction

This research deals with the position and image of women in the Holy Qur'an, despite what this image represents negatively or positively. The research presents with some examples the great role of pioneering women in building and establishing nations, also the image and status presented by the Holy Quran, and the human dignity that women have attained. She is the person who is honored according to the Qur'an, based on justice and fairness in a manner befitting the image that the Creator wanted for women, and her fairness before human efforts mess with her affairs, and she creates an issue to women's injustice, neglect, humiliation and marginalization.

The research problem emerges through the ancient and modern relevance of the necessity of fairness and liberation of women, as such repercussions have invaded the Arab and Islamic world from international charters, agreements and ideologies, as if they come with a race between them in the Arab-Islamic sphere for the liberation of women and victory for them.

Therefore, the importance of research on this issue has become obligatory to show the great care of Islam for the human being in general, and to focus on what gave women the status of competition with men, but rather that be just to both sexes equally in reward and punishment, and even in the style of speech, as the speech did not ignore the woman, but rather reveals what she has and owes, and limits what the disinterested human beings have tried to attach to our world and our society.

This study aims to uncover the ambiguity of some points, and clarifies the ambiguous understanding of some claimants and those demanding justice for women from Islam's oppression and its power over her, and shows Islam's vision of women and the great position that they have assumed as mentioned in the texts of the Holy Qur'an.

This study also aims to confirm what was presented by many studies that have shown many aspects in this field. In order to always confront those who deny the status of women in the Holy Quran.

This study also aims and calls for the necessity to delve into the understanding of the Qur'anic text and its objective interpretation away from the whims, a creative interpretation that raises the suspicion of following whims of the scholars and successive studies "Do you believe in part of the Scripture and disbelieve in part" Al-Baqarah 85

Then focus on understanding the original text without the need to import ideas and texts that may be included in the classification of alternatives or clarifications. "A Book whose verses are perfected and then presented in

detail from [one who is] Wise and Aware" Hūd 1. Perhaps this proposition will be a call for fairness and the failure of some studies to resort to what the other has, intentionally or unintentionally.

Among the most important objectives of this study is also to reveal the method and methodology with which the models of women are presented in the Qur'an text, and to reveal some of the clear wisdom for which these models were developed.

This study tries to answer some of the questions that continued to revolve in the minds of human beings until they appeared in the Arab and Muslim societies and started to worry them as well, women or men alike, among these questions:

1. What is the problem and where it comes from?
2. What are the social and cultural implications of it, and what is the size of the similarities and differences in the reflection of its effects?
3. What is the treatment method, and does this method differ in different societies?
4. What is the effect of different perspectives on the complexity of the problem, and do diagnostic errors have an effect on the nature of adjustment errors?
5. What are the features of perception errors, and what are their effects on determining remedial steps?

The study resorted to a combination of a number of approaches and research methods that had to be pursued in order to reach the maximum possible degree of achieving the desired goals, among the most prominent approaches adopted by the study are the deduction and analysis approach, and the induction and abstraction approach, this is to ensure the connection between the theoretical and the practical sides, which leads us to the closest thing that can be imagined of objectivity in identifying the features of this problem.

As for the previous studies, many studies have been viewed that dealt with this issue in part or with some expansion, including by way of representation but not limited to:

A study in title "Features of the strong, virtuous woman's personality in the Qur'anic narrative approach, in light of the changes of eras" by Dr. Dalal Mahmoud Shatnawi. One of the most important things the researcher focused on is one of the most important features of the strong, virtuous woman's personality in the Qur'an narrative approach, that are features derived from a divine source which is the base of the sources, and the most correct and authentic. As the Quranic stories came to describe the events in an accurate, comprehensive, integrated, purposeful and clear manner, then some research and studies that aimed at literary study and partly dealt with women, such as the book "Narrative Art in the Holy Qur'an" by Muhammad Ahmad Khalaf Allah, and a study by Dr. Suleiman Al-Tarawneh which is a literary textual study in the Qur'anic story, "this textual study of the Qur'anic story has focused its mainly on the linguistic message, and avoids as much as possible the knowledge of the semantic message in accordance with the methodology followed in the literary text specifically. Therefore, this study has worked on the approach of the Qur'anic text as a literary approach, and it intertwines with its components, so the (literary) textual function dominated here over all other functions. Abdul Salam Ahmed Al-Ragheb study in his book "The Function of the Artistic Image in the Holy Qur'an," in which he saw that the character of women in the Qur'anic story is secondary, not essential.

Then some studies that attempted to distort the meanings of the texts in order to conform to the goals and objectives of their writers who advocated the liberation of women and fairness from the injustice that befell her. There are many studies that have studied women in the Qur'an, and in the Qur'an stories in particular. Some of them focused on women in the lives of the prophets, such as Dr. Yassin Ghadban, and the study of Sheikh Al-Saadi in his book "The Stories of the Prophets" in which he dealt with women from among the Quranic stories, and the study of Sawsan Fahd al-Hawal in her book "Women in the Qur'anic Perception," as she made a comparison between the position of women in ancient societies and their position in Islam and explained that in many aspects.

Most of these studies confirmed that women have a great role in the lives of the prophets, and spread the call or stand against it. What distinguishes this research endeavor and sincere study is the statement of the position of women and their role, which is no less important than the role created by men in every time and place, through the presentation of Qur'anic models, and the research did not limit to Qur'anic stories, rather scopes was the Qur'anic text in its breadth and depth, through the models presented, emphasizing the unity of the soul to which the human beings, men and women, refer, denying and disputing the advocates of the liberation of women from Islam's injustice to women, and denying the inferior view of this fair approach to human beings in general, and this approach came in the research through the outlook, the comprehensiveness of this issue and exploring its depths to find out the essence of the issue, and unveil the origins of its emergence.

The study was divided into an introduction, a preface, two axes, and three topics.

The first axis: the origin to which humanity belongs.

The second axis: Show pictures and examples of equity in the holy Qur'an for women.

As for the first topic, entitled "The Mother in the Quran", includes the following examples:

- A. Eve, the core of humanity.
- B. B. Hajar, (Ismail's mother).
- C. Mother of Moses.

D. Mary(Maryam) - peace be upon her -

The second topic is titled “The Woman the Wife in the Qur’an”, and it consists of the following examples:

- A. Eve’s the first wife.
- B. B. Asia daughter of Muzahim.
- C. Lot's wife □ .
- D. Noah's wife □ .
- E. Al Aziz's (the governor of Egypt) wife.

The third topic deals with the leader woman model, includes:

- A. Balqis, Queen of Sheba.

Here, it must be noted that the three chapters did not come equal, as the nature of the study and the presentation of the models required this difference. Then the study ended with a conclusion that contained both findings and recommendations, and the research included margins and references.

Preface

Islam and all nations of the earth came to demean women and underestimate their rights, and the most that they attain in terms of appreciation is the recognition of their human origin only. Not to mention the recognition of her dignity and fairness and her approach to men in rights and duties. Then Islam came with the Qur’an as a constitution and an organization to emphasize care for women, display their images and conditions, and emphasize their important influence on the movements of individuals and groups and the fluctuations of events, just as it cares for the human being with his sexuality. To show the correct image that God wanted people to be, and here it is possible to solve many intellectual problems and suspicions related to the correct perception of the roles of all people, especially the role entrusted to women and their mission in this life, as the woman is the owner of the fabricated cause, and she is the one who is subjected to injustice. Restrictions were imposed on her, as portrayed by advocates of westernization and those who raised the banner of women's liberation. These theorists have distorted the position of Islam on women, so that religion has become for many people an accuser that needs someone to defend it, so they made the case for the liberation of women, because people do not move without a cause that bother them. Therefore, they worked on advocacy campaigns and gaining the support of ordinary people and specialists to fabricate that women are an issue that needs discussion and must be defended, and therefore they talk a lot in various media outlets, and they have always played and are still on this tendency that women in our societies are suffering and oppressed and do not obtain their full rights, and that men have taken everything, and so on until people feel that there is a cause for women, while they are in our society and when contemplating they do not exist”.

They took several paths to reach their set goals, including, for example, their saying that men take precedence over women in creation. Here we say, that this matter is due to human nature and common sense, because the nature of human beings required the advancement of men over women in this part, and this is due to human nature, not the Qur’an. The interpretation of this indicates that the issue is not related to a specific society, and the attempt to attach this issue, which has become an accusation in our society, is a deliberate attempt aimed at undermining it, and the reason for this is the alienation stemming from the admiration for the culture of the strong, and these admirers forget that this force is not a permanent force, so the continuity of the situation is impossible. Then, the power of the other that we are running after is not a civilized force as much as it is a civil force, and there is a wide difference between the power based on the depth of civilization and the power based on the shallowness of civilization resulting from the military victory, which often does not indicate civilization or civilization.

Since the problems to be solved are only a reflection of the social condition in any society, the utilitarian scholars among them and imitators who transferred social problems to other societies and tried to dress them up for our society, and accordingly, the difficult confusion between the problems arising in these societies and our society has occurred. Attention must be drawn to the fact that there is a big difference between our social life and their social life, so what dilemmas that have arisen with them does not necessarily arise with us, and perhaps the inability of these scholars to deep studies in our society, and their resort to taking ready-made studies on other societies, is what stands behind that confusion in many cases.

Scholars from among our fellow countrymen began to imitate this sterile tendentious theorizing and gasp behind the advocates of progress. Those who are aware of the status of women, as they are the cornerstone of the family, and its strong side, so their most dangerous goals were and still are the destruction of the family and society through women.

We acknowledge that there is a prejudice that reaches to what is sometimes described as the great about the right of women in all societies, each according to the social status entrenched in it, and our Muslim community is one of these societies, and the reason for that prejudice is not due to religion as much as it is due to the nature of society, this society and its various conditions, so traditions play its role is just as the social backwardness imposed on our societies plays its role as well, and the reason for injustice and underdevelopment together does not fall on the burden of religion as much as it falls to the social nature that has been forged and modified through the accumulation of time that our society has transmitted harsh shifts in various forms of life and its

aspects, and perhaps a fair view that cannot be to conclude, however, that the injustice inflicted on our societies has included them in their entirety without allocating to the woman themselves, for the man also suffers from the general state of injustice that women suffer, so the state of oppression is related to a person's sexuality.

This social and political penetration has a great impact on coloring the condition and backwardness of our society, with a focus on what concerns women, knowing that this effect is not limited to women in particular, but rather on people, and hence the treatment of the issue of women is not limited to this issue alone, but rather within the framework of treatment as for what is happening with the entire nation, and returning the situation to what it ought to be, as for the diagnosis to be limited to the fact that the nation's weakness is the result of what afflicted women from alleged injustice so that people feel that women have a special status without the rest of society, this is a deliberate plan, the goal behind exaggerating the issue so that people turn their necks to, so that these people present their toxic solutions; It is also intended, and specifying the issue as the issue of women as well as avoiding the scientific view; In contradiction to objectivity and impartiality, the viewer in this way does not intend at all to treat the fabricated defect, because it ignores the real causes and lacks comprehensive treatment of the emergence of this problem and returning it to its original roots.

In this study, we have publicly removed ambiguity and illusion from the delusional, and we close the doors as much as we can in the face of beneficiaries, and clarify the image for the first issue and the main focus of this study, by explaining how the Holy Qur'an portrays and describes women? What are assigned to her great roles? And how she attained a great position, a high status, a bright image, and human dignity, which God blessed her, through the realistic characteristics of the Qur'anic approach in its presentation of the human model and the entire human race, sometimes displaying images of men, and others of women. Both cases are timeless models that humans cannot fault in every society and every generation.

As if these models came in order for the Qur'an to clarify this familiar difference, and to acknowledge the existence of these types and the necessity of their eternal existence in this life. The research will review some of these models on the way they are presented in the Qur'an through direct discourse of women or through Qur'anic stories, also through images, embodiment and diagnosis of the accidents that women have gone through, and the reactions issued by them to all of that. The Qur'anic image of women has reached the summit in influencing the recipient, because it stirs both religious and human feelings, as it shakes the depths of the human being, because it depends on the facts of life, the facts of existence, through the presented scenes, and short images, the models drawn, the occurring events, and the past stories. Emotional influence is its extent, and the outlets of the soul are opened to receive influence through thought, conscience, mind and feeling together (). And when the researcher intends to study the Qur'an, he must be well aware that he will face many challenges, the first of which is that he will be in the presence of a great and deep text from a wise and mighty one that was revealed in that fertile period of the history of the language's brilliance, clarity and splendor, at that time when the language was flowing over The tongues of its people smoothly and easily, and Arabic was and still is the miraculous template of the Qur'an. This book, which was a miracle, challenged people who had mastered eloquence and rhetoric, tormented the statement and witnessed its miracle and penetration of their language and felt helpless and overwhelming in front of its splendor and mastery. The people of the language realized that if people and the jinn gathered together and some of them were in alliance with one another, they would not come up with something similar to it, "Say, "If mankind and the jinn gathered in order to produce the like of this Qur'an, they could not produce the like of it, even if they were to each other assistants." Al-Isrā 88

The Qur'an challenged the Arabs by that, so they were powerless, and they acknowledged their inability and shortcomings to match it or come up with an example "in expression and image, and they are eloquent and clear, and its expressions are familiar to them, but its expressions and images are vivid and clear".

This was the time when the Noble Qur'an was revealed to Quraysh, as the pure Arabic pediment helped to perceive the artistic beauty of the Qur'an, beautiful depiction, and miraculous expression. How are we today when the melody, defects, and the longevity between us and the purity of the language and the glorification of the Qur'an have afflicted them?

As for the other challenge, it is represented in the prestige and fear that the student experiences when he intends to delve into the depth of this great book, especially that it is from God, so how can we surround the least of it in isolation from the topic that the researcher is addressing to research in a renewed book whose wonders do not expire, and the researcher does not surround Strangely enough, but in any case an attempt to get close as possible. The origin of humanity: God created Adam and then Eve to build this universe. Meaning that the formation of life in its human element of a man and a woman is a natural division and was not in vain in any way, then he broadcast from them men and women and gave them the mind to contemplate everything that is happening in this universe. It is not set in the interest of one individual, but it is prescribed in the interest of the community in general, and the divine law is reflected in the fact that humanity is two: a man and a woman ".

So how do they want in the name of rights, renaissance, and women's liberation to interpret this divine law wrongly and absurdly, especially with those imitators who have made men an enemy of women, and the law is an enemy of women, and it is imperative that women enter with all this system in quarrels and struggles that they sometimes improve with competition or empowerment, and this may be expected and accepted by non-

Muslims who deny the Qur'an, for example, or who reject Islam and its law, but the unfortunate matter is that such calls come, and these movements come from Muslims who believe in the Qur'an, and they must remember well that human origin is one, and that difference is a natural innate feature that came to achieve human integration, so disagreement did not come to find difference.

The advocates of estranging women and dropping them from the lofty position in which the Book of God placed them, and distorting their realistic image, have several methods, including calling for women's oppression and their inequality with men. Seeking absolute equality between a man and a woman is inconsistent with God's instinct that he has created the two sexes. The same sex, a man or a woman, cannot ask for equality among all its members. Rather, the whole life is corrupted if such equality is desired. It is based on distinction, variation and difference. If the gender of men cannot be equal, how can the gender of men and women be? The great Islam provided the principle of justice and fairness among the children of Adam to ensure the continuity and integrity of life. And God created human beings from one soul, and this soul is the basis of human beings, and Adam's reference to the (one soul) is equal to that of his wife Eve, so they are the same. The soul is the reference for each of them, and everyone who was from their offspring until Judgment Day.

The soul is the basis of human creation, as is the text of the Noble Qur'an in many places: "O mankind, fear your Lord, who created you from one soul and created from it its mate and dispersed from both of them many men and women. And fear Allāh, through whom you ask one another, and the wombs. Indeed Allāh is ever, over you, an Observer". An-Nisā 1

This soul, which God has mentioned in more than one place in the Holy Qur'an, does not originally bear a sexual characteristic, neither male nor feminine, so neither man nor woman can claim the origin and the fact that Adam was earlier in creation does not mean that he is the origin? Because he is the origin in the chronological sense, not the origin in the existential sense, and so is Eve".

As for the advocates of liberation and theorizing, some of them claim that women are a branch of men, and this in their account is deficiency and weakness, and if they want to benefit from this partiality and its philosophy in accordance with the policies drawn up, then they say that the woman is a branch of the man, this is injustice to the woman and must be fair.

The reference of the whole matter is the soul that does not carry any sexual referral, it is one soul as stated in the Holy Qur'an (from one soul). And in this of the existential equality what it contains. As for the feminization contained in its wording, it is according to the habit of Arabic linguistic usage, not except in the manner that the Arabs mean in their morphological formulas, which may be feminized and remembered, without feminine sexual or masculinity, as in their feminization of the sun and making the moon masculine.

The one soul affirms the concept of the source unity of soul and body, for they are the same in that, The one soul affirms the concept of the source unity of soul and body, for they are the same in that, O mankind, fear your Lord, who created you from one soul and created from it its mate and dispersed from both of them many men and women. An-Nisā 1

This fact is repeated in many places in the Qur'an. Because God knows the stubbornness of his creation of he said: "It is He who created you from one soul and created from it its mate that he] might dwell in security with her. And when he [i.e., man] covers her, she carries a light burden [i.e., a pregnancy] and continues therein. And when it becomes heavy, they both invoke Allāh, their Lord, "If You should give us a good [child], we will surely be among the grateful." Al-A'raf 189

And also: "He created you from one soul. Then He made from it its mate, and He produced for you from the grazing livestock eight mates.[1342] He creates you in the wombs of your mothers, creation after creation, within three darknesses, That is Allāh, your Lord; to Him belongs dominion. There is no deity except Him, so how are you averted? Az-Zumar 6

The soul, then, is the essence of being human, male or female. From here, God reconciled the sexes in the general mandate. The principle of the mandate lies in the words of God: Then their Lord answered them to them that I will not waste the work of a worker among you, male or female, of some of you who are related to you by God (). Or femininity, but the characteristic that he is seen by is being (a worker), or non - worker. The soul is created and created according to the instinct that God desires, and this is the meaning of the words of Sheikh al-Islam Ibn Taymiyyah: So the soul, by its innate nature, if left, would be appreciative of God in divine love; for his love, worshiping Him does not associate anything with Him. But it is corrupted by what adorns the demons of mankind and the jinn, in what some of them suggest to some of the falsehood "()" (15). Hence, God addressed man as a (soul) by way of sharing. That is, without discrimination in the origin, whether the speech is related to training, or it is related to assignment. Allah says: [To the righteous it will be said], "O reassured soul. Return to your Lord, well-pleased and pleasing [to Him], and enter among My [righteous] servants, And enter My Paradise." Al-Fajr 27 -30, also said: "And fear a Day when no soul will suffice for another soul at all, nor will intercession be accepted from it, nor will compensation be taken from it, nor will they be aided" Al-Baqarah 48, He also said: " No person is charged with more than his capacity". Al-Baqarah 233

All the texts we have reported in this context and the many other texts mentioned in the Book of God are all indicative that the human soul is essence, and that it is the subject of divine discourse. Hence, it is this soul that

Islam intended to adorn and beautify, and perhaps we will realize some of its ruling on imposing the covering on women. So that the face of the image does not overwhelm the sky of the soul, which is the true semiotics, and is the basis of distinction in Islam. "The physical semiotics of women has an aesthetic aspect that performs a reproductive function with the first intention and an erotic function with the second intent.

That is the existential root of women's beauty, and its original intent, yes, it has a subordinate or dependent intention, which is permissible, sensual adornment, for this adornment is natural. That is, in an innate sense. The man tends to be attracted to female beauty, but to serve the original intention of the offspring, and that is not intended for itself. The problem with the human being today, male and female, is that they have turned the scales! So they made the intended subjective original, and the original consequently; the facts of life were thus transformed for them, from high humanity to fallen idiocy, and from spiritual pleasure to lustful pleasure. The advocates of women's liberation found in women's clothing and decency a ladder to escalate in pursuit of their goals, so they tried to reach through the dress and modesty of women, which is at the root of its status based on serving those great overall objectives in religion, and on respecting human existence and not despising it, or falling into it. The darkness of pure animal life. The dress of women, as approved by Islam and all the monotheistic religions, before it was tampered with, has a fundamental content that strikes deep in the unseen! It is an existential dimension! Is related to the existential nature of women in terms of being a human being who enjoys the human dignity that God granted to the children of Adam? O children of Adam, let not Satan tempt you as he removed your parents from Paradise, stripping them of their clothing to show them their private parts. Indeed, he sees you, he and his tribe, from where you do not see them. Indeed, We have made the devils allies to those who do not believe. Al-A'raf 27

God created human beings from one soul, and this soul is the basis of creation, and then the Qur'anic discourse for women started from the principle of the total discourse of man, since the first discourse of the human soul was, then the creation was a man and a woman, each with its own characteristics and characteristics that are consistent with its role in the reconstruction of the earth and carrying honesty. As for the points of difference between them, this is due to the complementary nature between masculinity and femininity, and not to a congenital deficiency in the nature of the woman, for the man may lack something to complete the woman, and the woman may lack in something that the man completes. In pursuit of the formation of the natural innate need between them, and a desire for permanent meeting and ensuring the sustainability of life and the reconstruction of the universe until Resurrection.

Images of fairness for women in the Qur'an:

Islam did not injustice women and did not deprive her of freedom, nor did it suppress her creativity and freedom as advocates for the emancipation of women claim, but it gave her sufficient freedom that is consistent with her feminine nature in all her stages and conditions, and the natural roles entrusted to her, and this claim did not come in vain, and it is possible to throw it away by Islamic legislation. But this legislation to which criticism is directed was issued by the Creator who knows the nature of creation, so it was in harmony with this nature that God created "Does He who created not know, while He is the Subtle, the Aware" Al-Mulk 14, Since the Noble Qur'an included women with adequate justice, and did not exceed the limit that guarantees her femininity, emotion, delicacy, and uniqueness, and here it is necessary to point out that clear and clear difference between justice and equality, justice is one of the most important requirements of the right approach, while equality is far from that The alleged advocacy for women is distorted until it leads her to a clear and clear injustice against her, to the point of attacking her nature, which resulted in the emergence of the third sex under the pressure of heavy living. As a matter of unjust equality, women carried what they could not bear of the burdens of life, as their alleged supporters deviated with them to work that required muscle energy, which led many in Western society to deliberately abuse hormones that gain them muscle strength in order to be able to carry out the harsh actions imposed on them. Unjust equality, as their femininity was eliminated, as if those who were keen to advocate for women wanted human creation with the same gender, which is the gender of men.

In this normal context in harmony with human nature, the Qur'an presented a number of images and models that indicate its concern for humankind in its two sexes.

The Qur'an has presented in its texts and stories its different models and many situations in which the woman varied between weakness and strength, between emotional equilibrium, and being drawn after passions, and between a clumsy woman who is unable to manage her affairs, to a leader who makes nations and takes care of peoples. Ultimately realist, it simulates the past, present and opposite times, and simulates the difference and contrast of societies from time to time to form images of people of their different types. Women and their models, and what strengthens him from these images and models, and what denies him his dismissal and imbalance. The research will present images of the Qur'an's justice and fairness to women:

First: Divine justice includes both men and women in the principle of assigning them to legal rulings, with some difference in some detailed provisions regarding the nature of each of them.

Second: Justice and equity between the sexes in the worldly and eschatological reward and punishment. He says in the sentence: "The believing men and believing women are allies of one another. They enjoin what is right

and forbid what is wrong and establish prayer and give zakāh and obey Allāh and His Messenger. Those - Allāh will have mercy upon them. Indeed, Allāh is Exalted in Might and Wise" At-Tawbah 71.

Third: The Noble Qur'an did justice to the woman in taking her right, and the judge heard her grievance and gave her the opportunity to express it, just as it is the case for men.

Fourth: The woman is free to own her money and dispose of it.

Fifthly: The woman is free to choose her husband, so she is not forced to do what she does not want, a woman must be proud of her femininity and what God has endowed and love for motherhood, running the house, raising men, and offering forgiveness for how these rescuers portray the home and the task of motherhood, custody and guardianship of men. The husband is a compelling jailer, and the guardianship is a prayerful sword, and motherhood is a pastoral reproduction, until he creates in the souls of women a nose, disgust and a search for a departure without restrictions".

Types of women in the Holy Quran:

The Noble Qur'an depicts the human nature of women for us, through various methods, and the goal is not to portray women as an angel or a devil, but rather to portray this nature in them, to direct their preparations towards goodness and righteousness, and to present the appropriate model for chastisement and emulation. The Qur'anic image interacts with reality to achieve demolition and construction at the same time, demolishing paganism and building the edifice of Islam. It is an artistic image that proposes an alternative to the reality of *Jahiliyya*, and provides a vivid model for the new reality, and through the positive interaction between Islamic thought and reality, the artistic image in the Qur'an is distinctive. With her artistic formation based on a clear Islamic vision of life, the universe and man. Hence, the presence of women in the Book of God emerges with a positive realism: "Her presence did not lead to a satanic existence, to be a cause for her disdain, contempt and aversion to her, and she was not covered by an angelic dress that would be a reason for her praise and exaggeration". When the Quranic text presents pictures of the mother, it is as if it says that these are the types of women that will be present between you, with you and in your societies, and when it presents images of a wise woman with a strong personality who is distinguished by her ability to enter the fields of leadership and politics, he tells about the presence, or say about the necessity of the presence of such women In societies, men are asked to make room for it, and not to despise such a presence without which there would be defects and deficiencies in managing life affairs, and the entrances of doubters and idolaters, enemies of both worldly and religion, abound. Here, the research will present some examples of the types of women as mentioned in the Book of God, and how he approved them and emphasized their presence and active participation.

The first topic: the mother woman model

When writing about woman as a mother, one must contemplate and imagine the deep, flowing meaning of the camp, and the broad connotation of the expression "mother," because this word suggests shelter and refuge.

First: Eve

Eve, the mother of humanity, represents the first example of the mother, woman and wife that God created from one soul, a soul from which her husband was created. She is the first woman created by God, and the second creature that God made.

Eve was the one who drove Adam and out of Paradise, and she was the one who instigated and motivated him to eat from the Tree. This is contrary to what was proven by the Qur'anic text, which was repeated in many places. From Eve and her husband, allhumans descended, and she was the nucleus of mankind and the mother of all creation, so she must have endured the consequences of early motherhood, its apparent burdens, and her severe pain.

Second: Hajar - peace be upon her -

Another example from the Quran of a sincere sacrifice of motherhood, is Hajar - peace be upon her - the mother of the Arabs, and the second wife of Abraham - that woman who was left by Abraham at the command of God - in Makkah where is no people, plants, or water. She feared for the life of her little baby so she sought to seek water between Safa and Marwah, the Qur'an drew the image of this mother, Hajar, at a time she was left alone except for a baby. The story goes on to describe Abraham's action when he and her son went to a valley in which there were no ears to be reaped, no seed to be eaten, and no fruit to be reaped? No human to speak with?"Our Lord, I have settled some of my descendants in an uncultivated valley near Your sacred House, our Lord, that they may establish prayer. So make hearts among the people incline toward them and provide for them from the fruits that they might be grateful".Ibrāhīm 37

Among the examples presented in the Qur'an text is the image of Abraham's wife Sarah mother of Isaac this lady who had reached an old age was a servant of the Prophet of God Abraham welcoming and serving his guests, so she was a model for the patient woman

Third: Moses mother

The Quranic text presented the image of this mother, who was tested by giving birth to a male son at the time of the tyrant of Egypt who saw that his end and death would be at the hands of one of the sons of Israel, to decide - after that vision - to slaughter male sons and keep the women, and because the problem in the story of Moses

appears by his birth, the story began on his birthday directly, "And We inspired to the mother of Moses, "Suckle him; but when you fear for him, cast him into the river and do not fear and do not grieve. Indeed, We will return him to you and will make him [one] of the messengers."Al-Qasas 7

The story of Moses began on his birthday, when conflict erupted in the soul of the mother. After she knew that Pharaoh had announced the killing of the children of Israel, and that God wanted to bless them that they would be empowered on the earth by the birth of the savior hero, this mother remained confused about what to do to her child, Moses' mother was facing two hardships: pregnancy, and the fear of thinking about the fate of her fetus.

The one who contemplates the suffering of this mother realizes well that she is worthy of the high position that our true religion has placed for her due to the hardship of pregnancy, the obstinacy of childbirth, and the fatigue of breastfeeding with the further fear of her children that they may suffer harm.

This is Moses's mother who began to provide her son with safety reasons since he was a fetus. Moses's mother did what God inspired her, and she stayed for a while, then God decreed that Pharaoh's soldiers would pick up her baby Moses. We can imagine the situation of a woman whose child fell into the hands of a child-slaughterer and a tyrant of the earth who knows no mercy. There is no doubt that the linguistic expressions are unable to present a complete, clear and accurate picture that shows the feeling of this woman, except for one phrase: "And the heart of Moses' mother became empty [of all else]. She was about to disclose [the matter concerning] him had We not bound fast her heart that she would be of the believers"Al-Qasas 10.

I believe among the secrets of displaying the mother's image, raising her status, venerating her position, and reminding the child of his mother's thanks for him to appreciate her. So to become good with her, justifies her, and flees from everything that hurts her, and it contains a message of reassurance to mothers and fathers, removing their worry and distress.

Fourth: Maryam

When Maryam - peace be upon her - is the focus of the lesson, it is necessary to go back to her early upbringing, and how she was enamored of God, so her mother, Imran's wife, vowed what was in her womb to God, free of all servitude to others, calling on God to accept her vow. "My Lord, indeed I have pledged to You what is in my womb, consecrated [for Your service], so accept this from me. Indeed, You are the Hearing, the Knowing."Al-'Imrān 35.

When the newborn was a female - unlike what she had hoped - this did not prevent her from fulfilling her vow, praying to God to protect her from all evil so that she would be able to perform what was prepared for him? "...and I seek refuge for her in You and [for] her descendants from Satan, the expelled [from the mercy of Allāh]. Āl-'Imrān 36

God blessed this vow that was represented by Maryam, for she was before she was born a vow from her mother to serve Jerusalem in Jerusalem and she was one of her aspirations, then God willing that she would become the mother of a blessed prophet and his birth a miracle, but that his life is full of miracles, and God willing that he would arise for this blessed female an entire nation.

Imran's wife did not withdraw from her vow when she gave birth to a female, and Mary did what she had vowed to do, but embodied a great example, as well as in the motherhood of Jesus, the son of Mary, and she was a sign of purity and fellowship to God, and believing in His words as described by the Holy Quran: "And [the example of] Mary, the daughter of 'Imrān, who guarded her chastity, so We blew into [her garment] through Our angel [i.e., Gabriel], and she believed in the words of her Lord and His scriptures and was of the devoutly obedient"At-Tahrīm 12

Maryam was a model of the pure and chaste female. The Quranic text brilliantly drew the feelings of this Virgin from fear and confusion when she followed her surprises. . And here a bitter despair and confusion formed for her about how to get out of what she is in, and her highest wishes were: Oh, I wish I had died before this and was in oblivion, forgotten." Maryam 23

As if we are living with the image and within it, we almost see her extreme turmoil as she returns her child to her people, bearing him and facing their blame, disapproval, and surrounded by their words: Something has come. They think that she has been a great denier, so they accused her of prostitution or something similar, by denying prostitution to her mother, "O sister [i.e., descendant] of Aaron, your father was not a man of evil, nor was your mother unchaste." Maryam 28

Often we find the woman and her personality in the Qur'an text, either in the highest level she reaches, to the lowest depth in which she can deteriorate, and Maryam here is a symbol of chastity, virginity, transcendence and purity. She occupies her place in life and performs the desired role of her. Some researchers of Qur'anic stories in particular say, "The place of women in the Qur'anic stories did not attract excitement and suspense, but rather they took the expected role of them in life, and that stories with an effective female component are the most vital Qur'anic stories, and the most portrayal of human feelings".

This model woman had reached perfection and purity, which made people compete for her sponsorship and care, and strive hard to attain this high position. "Indeed, Allāh chose Adam and Noah and the family of Abraham and the family of 'Imrān over the worlds"Āl-'Imrān 33, "So her Lord accepted her with good

acceptance and caused her to grow in a good manner and put her in the care of Zechariah. Every time Zechariah entered upon her in the prayer chamber, he found with her provision. He said, "O Mary, from where is this [coming] to you?" She said, "It is from Allāh. Indeed, Allāh provides for whom He wills without account." Al-‘Imrān 37.

Second topic: woman as a wife

The image of a woman as a wife in the Qur’an varied accordingly: Sometimes it represents the image of the unsuspecting wife, and the other the image of the stray and repulsive wife, the pious and believing woman who is in harmony with the belief in which her husband believes, and sometimes the naughty wife, and the woman contrary to the approach of her husband and her people, The self-confident woman appeared, the stubborn woman, the sincere woman, and sometimes the Qur’an shows you the image of the mother and wife who suffered from the agony of infertility, and the longing for offspring, and how after she had given birth to a child, and after a long time, and sometimes you find the image of the woman who broke her instinct, outraged modesty and complied with Passion and lust, and another image we find in the Qur’an text, which is the image of the wife who is characterized by modesty and chastity, then the image of the woman who has been accused and thrown in her honor while she is innocent, and the texts of the Holy Qur’an do justice to her, and the image of the patient woman who endures the hardship of life with her husband. These pictures all confirm what we go to, that the Qur’an, in its style and all its texts, not only showed the good side of women, and not only presented bright pictures, but women were present with all the types of characters, and with all the stability, movement, calmness and fluctuation of those characters.

The wife was not wronged in Islam rather that the Qur’an guaranteed her full and uncompromised rights, and looked at her comprehensively, fairly and complementarily, and safeguarded all her rights. Likewise, the woman has rights over her husband. She has the right of the marriage portion over her husband, and it is a pure gift that God has imposed on the woman, not in exchange for something that she must give except fulfilling marital rights, and it is her right alone "And give the women [upon marriage] their [bridal] gifts graciously. But if they give up willingly to you anything of it, then take it in satisfaction and ease".An-Nisā 4

The wife has the house and clothing that preserves her dignity "Lodge them [in a section] of where you dwell out of your means" At-Talāq 6, The wife has moral rights, and she is free to choose a husband: her father does not have the right to force her against whom she does not want, and Islam has urged the husband to behave with the wife kindly: so that some of her mistakes do not provoke him, or forget some of her abuse. "And live with them in kindness. For if you dislike them - perhaps you dislike a thing and Allāh makes therein much good" An-Nisā 19.

So, women enjoy human dignity that safeguards their rights and freedom, as they are among the common Muslims, good dealings shall be accorded to her as that is given to every human being, and she has the same rights as men.

First: Eve

The Holy Qur’an framed the relationship between Adam and Eve so that the personality of one would not overwhelm the other. Justice was clear in speech, reward and punishment, and in the primacy of creation and existence. Adam and Eve were created from a single soul that does not carry "in the origin a sexual characteristic, neither masculinity nor femininity. This is truly amazing. Neither man nor woman can claim that the origin of humans." The fact that Adam was earlier in creation does not mean that he is the origin.

The Holy Qur’an was fair to our mother Eve in what may be attributed to her that she is the reason for removing humanity from paradise, so the speech came clear as many of the verses address Adam alone and that he is the one who was whispered by the devil, and other verses in which the speech is shared and they have repented together, and they confessed their sin and they afflicted them from the leaves of Paradise, which is an evidence that nudity is a divine punishment, and atonement for it is only through concealment.

So, the image of the woman that God wanted is clear, and the position that God has bestowed on her is high, and if the skeptics try to leave bad and dangerous effect on the demolition of the family and to shake the status of the wife and husband together, they adorn to the wife that her obedience to her husband is a violation of her dignity and a diminution of her rights, and that she must prove her presence before him, for she is obligated to obey him in whatever command he directs. Add to that the extremists who read the texts of the Qur’an according to their interests, so they harden their dealings with their wives, forgetting the good example of the Prophet Muhammad and his honorable companions.

Second: Asya, the daughter of Muzahem, the wife of Pharaoh

When the meditator brings up the name of Asya, the wife of Pharaoh, it is necessary to remember the great ability of this wife, the eloquent judgment that she had, and the great skill that this woman possessed, as she was able to distort the planning of one of the greatest titans on earth. Her ability to influence Pharaoh and her good management of the situation had a great role in saving Moses. Asya embodied the image of the wise wife in her management and speech, and how she was able to contribute to saving the Prophet of God Moses, God says on

her lips "And the wife of Pharaoh said, "[He will be] a comfort of the eye [i.e., pleasure] for me and for you. Do not kill him; perhaps he may benefit us, or we may adopt him as a son."And they perceived not." Al-Qasas 9.

Asya played the greatest role in providing protection and care for the Prophet of God Moses, and her mind in him was sincere when she said: I love my eyes (She was able to maintain her personality independent from her husband despite his tyranny, stubbornness and authority, and she had her own belief that contradicts the doctrine of Pharaoh, and this is the greatest evidence that a woman is able to neutralize emotion, rely on reason, and take an attitude independent of what the husband takes, for this is Pharaoh's wife she was not seduced by the title of wife of the king of the earth. She was a model for a righteous woman who gave up all appearances of royalty and a soft life in palaces. She was not convinced of what her husband and his entourage owed, nor was she intimidated by his power and authority. In the story of Asya, the wife of Pharaoh, is a way out for women, a great lesson, and a good opportunity for misfortune, and in it there is a great amount of wisdom and sweet methods that enable a woman wife to be good in dealing with husbands, regardless of their varieties, varied patterns of thought, and their beliefs multiplied. From lack of patience, and good behavior in managing her life affairs. This is not a permission for the husband to control, domineering and arrogance, nor is it a call to women to submit and bow, but the Qur'an text presents models and it is good for every time and place, which man will find popular in societies despite their differences. Asia is patient and sympathetic, and hides her secret with God, and conquers Pharaoh, and participates in the making of the prophet of God Moses, so that she is a wonderful example that God strikes for his faithful servants: "And Allāh presents an example of those who believed: the wife of Pharaoh, when she said, "My Lord, build for me near You a house in Paradise and save me from Pharaoh and his deeds and save me from the wrongdoing people."At-Tahrīm 11.

Third: Lot's wife

And since the Holy Qur'an is fair and just in portraying women, justice requires realism in the presentation, and it is directed to all societies of the world, regardless of time and place. Therefore, the image of the woman came to the point of realism, so the angel did not come that did not know the error, nor did it come in a hideous way Repulsive, devoid of any commitment and any kind of responsibility, but the Qur'an text presented balanced, patient, accountable women leaders who are able to fulfill the requirements of life on its vigor and cruelty who manage matters with wisdom and high skill. We have presented some of these models that are valid for misfortune through the different stages of life. On the contrary, the Qur'an presented images of women and wives useful for exhortation. Among these models differing in their behavior:

Lot, the Prophet of God, the story of his people was linked to the coming of the angels to Abraham in the form of guest men, as they preached to him and his wife the boy and told him about the fate of the people of Lot. . It is difficult for a person to have an enemy such as a husband, son, brother, father, or close relative, so one of his relatives wronged, so how about the Prophet of God if the planner and conspirator is his wife?

This is an example for a wife who practices betrayal of faith with her husband and conspires against him. This type of betrayal is more dangerous than others. Because it is practiced with a prophet assigned to correct the belief of a nation, while other types of betrayal are only reflected on the personal level. As for betrayal, its reflection is more general and comprehensive, especially since marital (sexual) infidelity was definitely not mentioned. Because Lot's wife was living in a society that was peculiar to the human instinct, so the men of that society had lost their desire for men to come, not to women, as stated in the texts of the Holy Qur'an.

Fourth: A wife Another story and example of this kind of betrayal and hostility to the prophets' husbands is the woman of God's prophet Noah, this prophet who suffered a lot in the argument of his people who opposed him, His wife shared with them the mockery of her husband, the Prophet, and what he was doing, and she was mentioned in the Qur'an. "Allāh presents an example of those who disbelieved: the wife of Noah and the wife of Lot. They were under two of Our righteous servants but betrayed them, so they [i.e., those prophets] did not avail them from Allāh at all, and it was said, "Enter the Fire with those who enter" At-Tahrīm 10.

Noah has worked hard in calling his people to monotheism, but his wife was deeply involved in polytheism, drawing close to the gods and serving them, and when Noah called her for the unification of God, she did not respond, and she was one of the drowned.

When Noah was busy building the ark, his wife mocked him with those who were surprised at building the ship in the desert. When he told them that this ship would go on the sea with the grace of God when his command came, she accused him and her people of madness, and when the flood happened, his wife was not convinced until then and she was haughty and took refuge in a mountain, which she thought would protect her, but she sank in the end.

The thing that must be emphasized is that Noah's wife also had practiced betrayal in religion and was not in fornication, as God protects the women of the prophets from falling into immorality as a dignity for the sanctity of his prophets who strive to perform the messages of God. The betrayal from her is betrayal of disbelief and slander, not betrayal of adultery and immorality. .

Both Lot's wife and Noah's wife practiced betrayal with the two prophets of God, so Noah's wife used to tell people: He is crazy, while Lot's wife used to refer to the guests, because this betrayal was in religion and not

fornication, and God set an example for these two women to benefit with her from both sexes, in this a message of caution to the woman against these two women.

Al Azeez's (Governor of Egypt) wife

The example of Al Azeez wife and her companions came in the Quran to reveal the power of the woman, her wits and her vigor at all times and places, and how if a woman had these characteristics, the silence of men would prevail, their approval, or their inability to change.

This model came to many different lessons and sermons, including the statement of the infallibility and recommendation of the Prophet of God, Yusuf, also a kind of tribulations and that he faced during his journey in life, and this model also came to be a lesson and a sermon to women of the worlds.

Al Azeez woman begged with her beauty, her speech, her authority, the youth of Yusuf and his celibacy to achieve her goal, but Yusuf said: " [I seek] the refuge of Allāh" Yūsuf 51. And here is a reinforcement for the young people who strive to preserve the soul from following whims and desires, drifting in the mud of vices, how their reward is will be great in the hereafter. This image presented by the Qur'anic stories may have been one of its connotations, indicating the seriousness of the sedition of unclean women, and a warning to young people of both types.

Thus, the Quran, "The Guide to Creation, the Catalog of their Life, and the Constitution that organizes the affairs of their livelihood - are examples of the wife whose images have passed and will pass through the extension of humanity. These different models in her commitment or escapism, her domination or wisdom, would have had and will have different effects and extensions in which husbands, families and children will harvest the results whither good or bad.

The third topic: the woman leader like human progression, the progression of women was in the models presented throughout the Qur'an, and the model that imposes itself on the vocabulary of the research is a valuable model and an accurate standard for measuring and proving that women bear the highest responsibilities. It is known that "responsibility is a purposeful and wise process that directs human activity and makes it stand and will, so the responsible person turns into a purposeful person who has a destination and seeks to achieve and reach it."

This is how Belqis, the Queen of Sheba, who embodied a model for the upper class of women represented by the leading woman, here is the Qur'an that shows us the image of Queen Belqis, about which the hoopoe of Solomon was foretold, when the hoopoe said "Indeed, I found [there] a woman ruling them, and she has been given of all things, and she has a great throne" An-Naml 23. In the personality of this queen is a model of responsible, trustworthy, competent woman with expertise in managing matters, and adopting the principle of consultation before making any fateful decision regarding the matter of her kingdom, and this seems clear when the Prophet Solomon corresponded with her. The elders of her people for their advice on this royal letter to her she said, she said, "O eminent ones, advise me in my affair. I would not decide a matter until you witness [for] me" An-Naml 32. She dealt well with her people with the skill of her communication with them until she made them feel that she was one of them, and that the decisions made by her are joint decisions that come from both parties, so her role in decision-making is no less important than their role "Until you witness".

By doing so well, they would advise her and rely on her final decision, which is usually a summary of what they lead to her in terms of accurate description of the reality of their condition, their number, their willingness, and their obedience to her will to trust in her wisdom, and their response was after they showed their strength, "They said, "We are men of strength and of great military might, but the command is yours, so see what you will command" An-Naml 33. And here she chooses the wisest method of behavior, as she works on testing the opposite party and sends him a gift that decides based on his behavior about that what she will do, and this method indicates deep wisdom characterized by great experience and sophistication and the ability to policy the ocean and try to spare them the largest possible losses. And what happened was from the return of her envoys with her gift to her, so she knew full well that the spoil was not the goal of Solomon, for he was not a formal, traditional king, but rather the prophet the king. She and her people have the best options, as she subsequently became a partner to Solomon in the kingdom, and spared her people and his people the scourge of clash.

Perhaps it is important to mention here that this choice of Belqis was not based on the fact that the opposite side was a man, as the obedient men around her were many, but rather prophecy, faith, and peace, of good measure and administration; this made her suitable for the participation of the Prophet, King, in running a state that combines the royal form and the prophetic content to emerge after that as a model for the leader.

The Holy Qur'an has established a just rule and a fair principle in assuming positions and distributing roles, which is the principle of equal opportunities. The Holy Quran did not deny the Queen of Sheba that she had assumed this position in any part of the story, but rather made the general rule for assuming the responsibilities sufficient, regardless of any other considerations.

This model of women had components and characteristics that made everyone around her bear witness to her and approve of her course in managing the kingdom's affairs from the members of her surroundings, and from the Prophet of God Solomon. This is based on rational evidence by his ability, because he understood well any woman who was Belqis Saba, so he revealed her in her stature, and she, in turn, was enjoying the intelligence

that Solomon realized, In addition to the noble royal behavior, Belqis was also distinguished by the innate modesty that transcends the physical vulgarity that the queens used to excel as a feature of commoners.

The Noble Qur'an gave good and not-so-good examples and was not limited to women only, but rather it mentioned examples of men as well, and there are many models that this research does not expand to shed light on, with great roles that had their impact on the prophets, such as the model of the daughter, sister, sister Musa and the daughters of Shuaib. As mentioned above, Moses was surrounded by a group of women who accompanied him in the various stages of his life, saving him and moving with him in drawing up his plan and steps of his life who were the best example and foundations for women of the worlds, starting with his mother, Asya, his sister, and the two daughters of Shuaib.

Conclusion

We hope that we have succeeded in achieving the objectives of this study, to be an addition in the field of raising the suspicions that some have tried to attach to our society, and the imitators of the sons of Islam followed a blind tradition, with regard to women injustice and fairness. The study was divided into an introduction, a preface, two axes, and three topics. The research concluded the following results and recommendations: 1. The Qur'an depicts women in all their states as a wife, mother, or leader in a completely realistic manner, as is the way the Qur'an depicts characters. He did not portray her as an angel that does not make mistakes, and he did not portray her badly, and this is not strange, as all these images were derived from a divine source, which is the source on which he depends, as this image appeared describing events in an accurate, comprehensive and purposeful manner, and it is real personalities whom the Qur'an chose, so it is realistic with their persons and events. And its results. 2. Denying the suspicions about the Arab Muslim community from what the Westernization advocates and the thought invaders have attached to it about the status, position and role of Muslim women by transmitting a culture and the other's view of women and projecting them to our society. 3. Difference is an innate, natural feature that came to achieve human integration. The disagreement did not come to create difference. Rather, its existence is bound to be a coalition and complementarity in a society free of social diseases. 4. The origin to which both man and woman refer is the one soul from which God created the two and transmitted many men and women from them. 5. The research recommends the nation's fair scholars and other impartial scholars to more in-depth, impartial studies that will help stop incursion, return matters to their rightful place, and limit this blatant delusion. 6. The study recommends both men and women the necessity of respecting the great covenant between them as a couple, and the necessity for both sexes to believe in the role of the other and create opportunities that accelerate the development of life and make it a constructive element in society. 7. The necessity of giving women confidence and belief in their abilities, and striving to assume a position that accords with the principle of sufficiency and equal opportunities.

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